

TransformDairyNet project: A European effort to promote Cow-Calf-Contact dairy production systems

Dinu GAVOJDIAN^{1*}, Rachel ANNAN², Yael DOTAN³, Ioana NICOLAE¹, Madalina MINCU-IORGA¹, Siobhan MULLAN²

¹ *Research and Development Institute for Bovine, Department of Production Systems, Balotesti, Romania*

² *National University of Ireland, University College Dublin, School of Veterinary Medicine, Dublin, Ireland*

³ *Federation of Veterinarians of Europe, Schaerbeek, Belgium*

- **TransformDairyNet (TDN)** project aims to promote systems where calves are being kept with their dams for months, rather than being separated shortly after calving, as it is common in most conventional dairy farms.
- **Cow-calf contact (CCC)** systems have the potential to improve both animal welfare and health of farmed cattle and water-buffalo.
- The **TDN** project involves a number of 26 partners across Europe, including farmers, veterinarians, researchers, policymakers and industry experts, being funded by the European Union.
- One of the main aims of the project is to establish 11 National Innovation Practice Hubs (NIPs), in order to share knowledge about ongoing **CCC** practices, to develop innovative solutions to CCC challenges and guides for farmers, and to create a European network for exchanging information on sustainable dairy farming.

* *Corresponding author:*
 gavojdian_dinu@animalsci-tm.ro

- The project focuses on:
 - Driving dairy innovation through Living Labs in NIPs, fostering new ideas and testing sustainability solutions;*
 - Accelerating the adoption of CCC systems by mobilising a European Multi-Actor Network (EKIN) to address farmer needs and bridge knowledge gaps;*
 - Building capacity for long-term impact throughout collaboration and ensuring future-ready CCC knowledge sharing;*
 - Modernising the sector by combining science and practice to deliver validated best practices for CCC systems;*
 - Amplifying impact with digital tools and harmonised farmer resources to promote CCC systems widely.*

Figure 1: TransformDairyNet work packages

Photo credit: Julie Foske, NVI

TransformDairyNet project aims to enhance the resilience and sustainability of the dairy sector by creating a collaborative network to compile, co-create, and share practical knowledge and innovations in **CCC** systems across Europe.

Photo credit: Sabine Ferneborg, NMBU

Figure 2: TransformDairyNet consortium

The Romanian NIP has been operational since December 2024, coordinated by the Research and Development Institute for Bovine, further details: <https://transformdairy.net>

Acknowledgement: Project funded by the European Union (Grant no. 101133326). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or REA. Neither the European Union nor REA can be held responsible for them.